

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

The use of synthetic images of electrocardiograms (ECGs) and their applications in artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms.

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

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I. Data areas and data types

This project will generate a quantitative image-based ECG dataset comprising labelled images extracted from clinical ECG recordings. All images will undergo modification to simulate the composition of a real-world image-based ECG dataset. We estimate that the total file size, including administrative-generated data, will be up to 300 GB

II. Standards and metadata

All synthetic ECG images will be created in accordance with the recommendations outlined in the 'AHA/ACCF/HRS Recommendations for the Standardization and Interpretation of the Electrocardiogram' document (ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.106.180200). Data will be stored securely on local systems, with access restricted to the named research team. The data will be backed up daily using password-protected network storage. For easy accessibility, we will provide the metadata for all data as a table in comma-separated value (CSV) format in ptbxl database.csv, containing 28 columns, which can be easily accessed by using existing libraries in all common programming languages.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

This study utilizes secondary data as its primary input. All synthetic image data will be created using a publicly available repository of signal data. The original data is sourced from PTB-XL, the largest freely accessible clinical 12-lead ECG waveform dataset to date, consisting of 21837 records from 18885 patients, each 10 seconds in length (physionet.org/content/ptb-xl/1.0.0/).

IV. Secondary use

The methodology of this project outlines a framework that other fields can use to generate extensive, realistic synthetic patient datasets, reducing the need to continuously create new patient datasets prospectively

V. Methods for data sharing

To ensure long-term accessibility and discoverability of the data, it will be accompanied by comprehensive metadata upon submission. The dataset will be made available on the Hugging Face Hub, a

centralised platform for disseminating open machine learning models, datasets, and demonstrations. This will enable individuals interested to access cutting-edge machine learning models and datasets with minimal coding requirements.

VI. Proprietary data

Apart from the permitted period of exclusive use, there are no restrictions on data sharing.

VII. Timeframes

All the relevant data will be openly available to other researchers in a timely manner, with as few restrictions as possible. We reserve the right not to share data until it has been published and we have obtained the required validation and impact.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

The data will be stored in Wave Form Database Format (WFDB), which contains two standard categories: MIT Signal files (.dat) and MIT Header files (.hea). This format is proposed by PhysioNet (physionet.org/about/software), which has developed into a de facto standard for the distribution of physiological signal data.